

Deliverable 7.7.1.1

DESIGNING A CONSORTIUM SERVICE PORTFOLIO –
NFDI4ENERGY'S CRITERIA AND PROCESS FOR INTEGRATING
SERVICES

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D7.7.1.1 Designing a Consortium Service Portfolio – NFDI4Energy’s Criteria and Process for Integrating Services

Florian Kotthoff (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3666-6122>)¹, Alexandro Steinert (<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7207-1005>)¹, Oliver Werth (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6767-5905>)¹, Stephan Ferenz (<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9523-7227>)^{1,2}, and Astrid Nieße (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1881-9172>)^{1,2}

¹OFFIS, Institute for Information Technology, <https://ror.org/003sav189>, Escherweg 2, 26121 Oldenburg

²Carl von Ossietzky University of Oldenburg, Department of Computer Science, <https://ror.org/033n9gh91>, Ammerländer Heerstraße 114-118, 26129 Oldenburg

Published by

OFFIS, Institute for Information Technology, <https://ror.org/003sav189>, Escherweg 2, 26121 Oldenburg

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General Information

Summary

Useful services that help researchers to better deal with their research data and software and make them FAIR are a key outcome of NFDI4Energy. However, deciding what qualifies as a service and which services should be included in a consortium's service portfolio can raise questions that an NFDI consortia has to be aware of.

Based on previous works from NFDI, EOSC, and other consortia, we present the current status of the selection and onboarding process for services into the NFDI4Energy Service Portfolio. We define what constitutes a NFDI4Energy Service and outline the requirements for a service to achieve full NFDI4Energy Service status. These requirements include legal clarity, operational readiness, documentation, user support, and interoperability with relevant standards for service provision. The NFDI4Energy Service Portfolio supports FAIR data management, aligns service understanding and development, and contributes to the broader NFDI strategy. With this work, we want to document our service selection process, base it on clearly defined rules, and provide guidance to consortia that have not created a service portfolio yet.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

An NFDI4Energy Service Portfolio will list services that are developed within other Work Packages. These services are *Best Practices Service* (Task Area 1 and 8, short: TA1 and TA8), *Competence Service* (TA8), *Open Research Knowledge Graph* (TA8), *Open Energy Platform* (TA8), *Simulation-as-a-Service Hub* (TA5), *Leibniz Data Manager* (TA8), *Anonymization Service* (TA3) as well as Services that are developed outside the funded consortium.

Introduction

Conducting research in line with the FAIR principles [1] is challenging, especially for those unfamiliar with open science. To support these researchers, NFDI consortia aim to provide useful services that improve research data and software management and help make them FAIR. However, determining what constitutes a service and which service should be included in a consortium's portfolio can raise important considerations for the consortia. In this work, we will first review relevant works from other parties. Then we discuss the definition of services, as well as the requirements and processes to become an official NFDI4Energy Service.

Relevant Works from other parties

The **Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI)** defines the term „service“ and different categories of services in their White Paper: Interim Report References [2]. The purpose of a service portfolio on NFDI level is described as a selection of services that fulfill basic NFDI requirements and that are reliably available to researchers [3]. The NFDI outlines specific requirements for its future portfolio, including content, technical, and strategic aspects. On the European level, the service portfolio management of the **EOSC Hub** is described in [4]. They provide fourteen processes which are required to deliver well managed services. In the Service Portfolio Report of **NFDI4Biodiversity** [5], the consortium provides deep insights in their process of designing and maintaining their current service portfolio, which consisted of 80 services at the time of their report publication. They describe in detail their process of on-boarding new services and how they do quality assurance for services in their portfolio. The **Text+** Consortium shows their rather different approach in their “Guidelines for adding Text+ Services to the SSH Open Marketplace” [6]. They provide a marketplace where users can register new services after creating an account at the marketplace. These service entries will then be checked by moderators of the platform. This approach is rather bottom-up and sees the service owners responsible for creating good services.

NFDI4Energy Services

What is a Service?

We follow the service definition proposed in the “White Paper: Interim Report Reference” of the NFDI [2]:

A service in NFDI is understood as a technical-organisational solution, which typically includes storage and computing services, software, processes, and workflows, as well as the necessary personnel support for different service desks.

It is important to note that a software or software package itself is not considered to be a service. It can only become a service when the software is hosted somewhere and can perform tasks upon requests.

In NFDI4Energy, we use a technical-centric and a user-centric categorization schema for services. The technical-centric schema is the categorization of services based on the de.NBI service categories [7] with the extensions from [2]. These categories are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Service categories from a technical perspective as defined by [2], [7].

Category	Definition
Database	Software providing large amount of structured data to the user.
Library / API	Collection of pre-implemented functions for a specific task that can be accessed via a well-defined interface.
Workflow / Pipeline	Software that combines multiple tools / applications. They may be used locally or remotely via the internet.
Tool / Application	Software that can be downloaded and executed locally on the users' hardware.
Support / Consulting	Service with direct user contact for topics going beyond the support for the other services.
Web Application	Software that is installed on a server and can be used by users via a web page and the internet.
*Data Curation	If not included in support/consulting: "The activity of managing and promoting the use of data from their point of creation to ensure that they are fit for contemporary purpose and available for discovery and reuse. For dynamic datasets this may mean continuous enrichment or updating to keep them fit for purpose. Higher levels of curation will also involve links with annotation and with other published materials" [6]
*Training	Standalone training for self-study can be considered a technical service (usually a web application). Generally speaking, training materials often come in the form of specific measures or tutorials that are attached to a service and that are designed to improve the user's service experience. Our joint understanding of training as a stand-alone service, however, is not limited to the above and includes materials designed for education in all fields of research data management.
*Storage	Provision of storage space for research data as a service to external users. Access is possible via web protocols.
Noted with * are categories added by NFDI in [2]	

From the user perspective, services can also be allocated to the different stages of a research data life cycle. Services can help in one or multiple stages: **Planning, Production, Analysis, Storage, Access, and Reuse.**

Figure 1: The Research Data Life Cycle.

This categorization helps to develop a User Interface for the portfolio with the idea of providing researchers the relevant services, depending on the stage they are currently in.

What are the requirements of an NFDI4Energy Service?

An NFDI4Energy service is sustainably maintained with the necessary infrastructure and personnel, ensuring interoperability with other services through standardization. Since not all services can directly adhere to these requirements, we distinguish two stages for services: Candidates and full NFDI4Energy Services. The **requirements for the Candidate Status** are:

- A1:** The service needs to be a service as defined above. It also needs to offer benefits for researchers, data stewards, or research software engineers in the energy domain.
- A2:** The service is maintained and provided by a member organization of NFDI4Energy in the NFDI association („Konsortium gemäß Satzung (KgS)“) (the service provider).
- A3:** The service has already surpassed its conceptualization phase and is available as a prototype (TRL 3-4 or higher). We want to make sure that during the onboarding process, all stakeholders have a clear idea about the service. Therefore, the service already needs to exist in its first version.
- A4:** If the service is based on software, the software repository is open source with a License approved by the Open Source Initiative [8].
- A5:** The service provider and representatives from the NFDI4Energy consortium agree on relevant services and standards that need to be considered by the proposed service. These specifications are discussed with the service providers based on a checklist (see Appendix). The specifications are a case-to-case decision, but in general the following requirements exist:
 1. Services with user authentication should use services that allow the authentication with existing accounts, such as university accounts. This could be ensured by integrating RegApp via the IAM4NFDI Base Service.
 2. Data Platforms should integrate a Terminology Service and offer Persistent Identifiers.
 3. Services that produce data must be compatible with metadata according to the NFDI4Energy Metadata Standard.
 4. Services should be interoperable with relevant other services from the NFDI4Energy Service Portfolio.

Finally, the requirements agreed upon are verified and accepted by a service committee from the KgS.

- A6:** Maintainers of the service commit to further develop their service, especially having in mind the work needed to fulfill the requirements defined in **A5**.

The **requirements for the NFDI4Energy Status** are:

- B1:** The service needs to be interoperable with relevant other services and relevant standards. Hence, the specifications defined in **A5** need to be fulfilled.
- B2:** A clear legal status for all relevant aspects is needed. First, a Terms of Service needs to clarify how the service can be used. Second, if the service produces or provides data of some kind, it

needs to be clarified how this data can be used. And third, the codebase of the service needs to have an open-source license attached.

- B3:** The service needs to be in operation - it needs to be more than a prototype. Hence, a TRL 7 or above is required.
- B4:** The service needs to be documented. This also means that tutorials are provided within the Best Practice service of NFDI4Energy. If the service is based on software, this software also needs to be openly documented. To increase the findability of the service, it is listed on relevant platforms.
- B5:** A support needs to be available for users, meaning there is at least an email address available for users seeking support.
- B6:** The Service provider commits to the NFDI4Energy reporting and provides relevant information and KPIs.
- B7:** To ensure optimal performance and mitigate potential security risks, the service requires ongoing proactive **maintenance** and an openly documented, sustainable operating model for at least the next two years.
- B8:** To ensure the secure usage of the service, appropriate **application security measures** need to be implemented. Service Providers need to state which sensitive information is collected, and which measures are taken to secure this data.

The requirements for both stages are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Requirements for the NFDI4Energy Candidate Service status and an NFDI4Energy Service status.

NFDI4Energy Candidate Service	NFDI4Energy Service
A1: Service for Researchers in the Energy Domain	B1: Interoperability with other Services and NFDI4Energy Standards (Defined in A5)
A2: Service Provider is member of NFDI4Energy KgS	B2: Clear legal status regarding usage of the service, the produced results, and the underlying codebase
A3: Service is available as a prototype – TRL 3-4	B3: Service in Operation – TRL 7-9
A4: The software of a Service is open source	B4: Existing Documentation Pages
A5: Defining Requirements for Interoperability with other Services and NFDI4Energy Standards	B5: Existing Contact details for support
A6: Maintainers want their service to become an NFDI4Energy Service and commit to further work	B6: Commitment to NFDI4Energy Reporting B7: Active Maintenance and sustainable operating model
	B8: Appropriate Application Security

How can a service become an NFDI4Energy Service?

As described above, the process consists of two stages. To become an NFDI4Energy Candidate Service, the candidate requirements must be fulfilled. In A5, the specifications are discussed between NFDI4Energy and the Service Providers. This ensures that the Service Providers get a rough idea of the work that needs to be done to become a full NFDI4Energy Service. It shall be noted here that this list only needs to be defined in a first version and can be adapted during the rest of the onboarding process. If the service fulfills these requirements, the service provider can contact the NFDI4Energy service coordinator, who will verify them and forward the service to a subgroup of the “NFDI4Energy Konsortium gemäß Satzung (KgS)”, the so-called Service Committee. This Committee will then vote by a simple majority on whether the service qualifies as an NFDI4Energy Candidate Service. By this vote, the committee also agrees on the defined requirement list. If approved, the service will be added to the Service Portfolio with a candidate status flag.

To proceed, services must comply with requirements B1 through B8, as these will be subject to a review by the Service Committee. Following this assessment, the reviewed service and accompanying report will be presented to the KgS, which will then render a final decision based on a simple majority vote. The status of an NFDI4Energy Service will be reviewed regularly and can be withdrawn by a vote from the KgS.

Figure 2: Process of how a service can become an NFDI4Energy Service.

How does a service benefit?

Successfully completing the onboarding process and becoming an NFDI4Energy service holds several benefits. These benefits include enhanced visibility within the energy research and industry communities through online promotion, showcase events, and workshops, as well as overall NFDI-wide recognition. Additionally, services that have undergone the onboarding review are entitled to utilize the "NFDI4Energy Service" label, serving as proof of their successful evaluation. Furthermore, the NFDI4Energy consortium will provide support in developing sustainable operational models for these services.

Deprecation of the NFDI4Energy Service Status

If a service no longer fulfills its defined requirements or is not properly maintained, its status within NFDI4Energy will be deprecated. The deprecation of a service's status is determined by KgS through a simple majority vote.

Conclusion

The NFDI4Energy Service Portfolio has four key goals: First, it provides a valuable starting point for researchers and data stewards to manage FAIR data in the energy sector. Second, it promotes a shared understanding of services and the value that lies in orchestrating and connecting services by common standards. Third, it offers relevant insights for discussions on sustainable service operating models within NFDI4Energy. Fourth, it allows NFDI4Energy to contribute to the overall NFDI service portfolio, aligning with the association's strategic plan [9].

References

- [1] M. D. Wilkinson *et al.*, "The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship," *Sci. Data*, vol. 3, no. 1, p. 160018, Mar. 2016, doi: 10.1038/sdata.2016.18.
- [2] L. Amelung *et al.*, "White Paper: Interim Report Reference," Nov. 2023, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.10101412.
- [3] C. Busse *et al.*, "Leistungsfähige Entscheidungsstrukturen für ein NFDI-Dienstportfolio - Impulse zu Kriterien, Entscheidungsverfahren und Portfoliomanagement," Zenodo, July 2025. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.16356843.
- [4] O. Appleton *et al.*, "EOSC-hub D2.6 First Service roadmap, service portfolio and service catalogue," July 2019, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.4598252.
- [5] M. Meister *et al.*, "Service Portfolio Report 2023," Zenodo, Sept. 2023. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.8327367.
- [6] S. Buddenbohm, L. Weimer, L. Barbot, E. J. Gray, N. Rissler-Pipka, and M. L. Jander, "Guidelines for adding Text+ Services to the SSH Open Marketplace," July 2024, doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.12657204.
- [7] M. Turewicz, U. Scholz, F. O. Glöckner, T. Dammann-Kalinowski, and M. Wittchen, *de.NBI service category-specific KPI selection and criteria*. Zenodo, 2022. doi: 10.5281/ZENODO.6597826.
- [8] "OSI Approved Licenses," Open Source Initiative. Accessed: Oct. 15, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://opensource.org/licenses/>
- [9] "Website - Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI): Verein." Accessed: Apr. 16, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.nfdi.de/verein/>

Appendix

Checklist of Requirements for NFDI4Energy Services

This checklist serves as a protocol and discussion foundation for a meeting between Service Providers and the NFDI4Energy Service Coordinator. The following topics need to be discussed:

- Compatibility with Base Services
- Compatibility with other NFDI4Energy services
- Compliance with NFDI4Energy standards
- Compliance with NFDI requirements

The goal of this checklist is to define what requirements the service needs to fulfill to become an NFDI4Energy Service.

Name of the Service:

Contact Person:

Compatibility with Base Services

IAM4NFDI

IAM4NFDI is concerned with connecting and expanding existing and emerging Identity and Access Management (IAM) systems in a way that researchers from different domains and institutions are able to access digital resources within NFDI as easily as possible, including access to and exchange with external infrastructures and resources like the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). A decentralised, federated IAM is required. This way, users from approx. 400 German research and higher education institutions plus approx. 5000 home organisations worldwide -number increasing - will be able to access services and resources provided by the NFDI Community Authentication & Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI).

Does your service need to integrate / be interoperable with this service?

Yes.

No, integration does not make sense.

No, integration is plausible, but out of scope for becoming an NFDI4Energy Service.

Explain:

If the integration is required, how is the progress here?

- Integration is complete.
- Integration is in progress.
- Integration is planned.
- Not started yet.

PID4NFDI

Persistent identifiers (PIDs) are central to FAIR research data management. However, different disciplines and different resources result in diverse requirements and the different NFDI consortia have different levels of maturity in PID implementation. PID4NFDI will design a work programme to build an NFDI foundation service on established PID infrastructures.

Does your service need to integrate / be interoperable with this service?

- Yes.
- No, integration does not make sense.
- No, integration is plausible, but out of scope for becoming an NFDI4Energy Service.

Explain:

If the integration is required, how is the progress here?

- Integration is complete.
- Integration is in progress.
- Integration is planned.
- Not started yet.

TS4NFDI

Terminology Services 4 NFDI (TS4NFDI) is a cross domain service for the provision, curation, development, harmonization and mapping of terminologies. It aims to facilitate consensus-building and interoperability of services across disciplines to achieve a shared knowledge representation and knowledge engineering framework. The service seeks to integrate and converge individual solutions into a standardized, interoperable, and sustainable service suite with Service Wrapper, API Gateway, mapping service and reusable GUI widgets.

Does your service need to integrate / be interoperable with this service?

- Yes.

- No, integration does not make sense.
- No, integration is plausible, but out of scope for becoming an NFDI4Energy Service.

Explain:

If the integration is required, how is the progress here?

- Integration is complete.
- Integration is in progress.
- Integration is planned.
- Not started yet.

Jupyter4NFDI

This service will simplify access, improve user experience, and extend Jupyter's reach to a wider audience within and beyond the NFDI. It plans to integrate with IAM4NFDI for access governance and to provide access to HPC resources from GCS and the NHR Alliance.

Does your service need to integrate / be interoperable with this service?

- Yes.
- No, integration does not make sense.
- No, integration is plausible, but out of scope for becoming an NFDI4Energy Service.

Explain:

If the integration is required, how is the progress here?

- Integration is complete.
- Integration is in progress.
- Integration is planned.
- Not started yet.

DMP4NFDI

DMP4NFDI is a centralised Basic Service for managing data management plans (DMPs) and software management plans (SMPs) across the NFDI. It will host the open-source DMP tool

RDMO, coordinate template creation, standardise content, and offer guidance and support to consortia staff responsible for DMPs. The service aims to enhance communication among stakeholders, support data collection and review processes, and foster interoperability by engaging consortia early on to refine requirements and develop standardised DMP templates. Ultimately, DMP4NFDI seeks to maximise the benefits of widespread DMP adoption by promoting interoperability and integration across the NFDI's research data ecosystem.

Does your service need to integrate / be interoperable with this service?

- Yes.
- No, integration does not make sense.
- No, integration is plausible, but out of scope for becoming an NFDI4Energy Service.

Explain:

If the integration is required, how is the progress here?

- Integration is complete.
- Integration is in progress.
- Integration is planned.
- Not started yet.

KGI4NFDI

KGI4NFDI advocates for a central and reusable Knowledge Graph Infrastructure (KGI) to enhance interoperability within the research domain and support the NFDI's objectives. It aims to provide essential components including a Knowledge Graph (KG) registry and a service for accessing KGs across NFDI projects. Additionally, the service intends to empower research communities to create decentralised KG instances using standardised approaches, technologies, and expertise. Through surveys, documentation, consulting services, and ontology harmonisation, the proposal seeks to optimise KG creation and foster standardised ontological practices, contributing to the "One NFDI" vision and promoting FAIR data principles. This initiative will complement international efforts, such as those of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), in advancing knowledge graph initiatives.

Does your service need to integrate / be interoperable with this service?

- Yes.
- No, integration does not make sense.
- No, integration is plausible, but out of scope for becoming an NFDI4Energy Service.

Explain:

If the integration is required, how is the progress here?

- Integration is complete.
- Integration is in progress.
- Integration is planned.
- Not started yet.

nfdi.software

nfdi.software aims to create a central marketplace to improve access to NFDI research software, addressing the needs of various scientific disciplines for sustainable research software use and development. It will link and coordinate independent developments within a federated data infrastructure, enhancing networking and contextualisation of research software as well as links to data and other research artefacts. The need for a central access point for research software of the NFDI consortia arises from the growing need of the scientific disciplines of the cultural sciences, humanities and social sciences, engineering and the natural and life sciences to ensure the sustainable use and further development. The platform will extract, standardise, and enrich metadata, and applies an AI approach, providing continuous monitoring of software relevance and acceptance by its users. By establishing standards and improving networking across the NFDI, the project will develop a 'Prototype for Integration' based on prior initiatives. As a central service, nfdi.software will harvest, aggregate and harmonise software metadata from NFDI consortia marketplaces and registries, and will provide back enriched and curated metadata in future.

Does your service need to integrate / be interoperable with this service?

- Yes.
- No, integration does not make sense.
- No, integration is plausible, but out of scope for becoming an NFDI4Energy Service.

Explain:

If the integration is required, how is the progress here?

- Integration is complete.

- Integration is in progress.
- Integration is planned.
- Not started yet.

RDMTraining4NFDI

RDMTraining4NFDI is concerned with offering training in the knowledge and skills required for research data management (RDM) to all NFDI consortia. The training encompasses data, software, and machine-learning models, and is intended for the consortia's staff, such as data stewards and trainers, as well as researchers within the respective communities. The core goal of this service is to develop a modular collection of foundational RDM training materials, along with documented, proven training formats and methods. By providing access to these resources, consortia can efficiently create their own community-specific adaptations of the training and build capacity rapidly. Additionally, the option of certification will be explored to establish quality standards and document the skills acquired by participants.

Does your service need to integrate / be interoperable with this service?

- Yes.
- No, integration does not make sense.
- No, integration is plausible, but out of scope for becoming an NFDI4Energy Service.

Explain:

If the integration is required, how is the progress here?

- Integration is complete.
- Integration is in progress.
- Integration is planned.
- Not started yet.

Compatibility with NFDI4Energy Services

OpenEnergyPlatform

A database where everybody can add, edit, and review data – as well as factsheets about energy frameworks and models.

Does your service need to integrate / be interoperable with this service?

- Yes.
- No, integration does not make sense.
- No, integration is plausible, but out of scope for becoming an NFDI4Energy Service.

Explain:

If the integration is required, how is the progress here?

- Integration is complete.
- Integration is in progress.
- Integration is planned.
- Not started yet.

Leibniz Data Manager

The Leibniz Data Manager is a CKAN distribution tailored for Research Data Management and was developed to support the aspect of better re-usability of research data. It enables FAIR and sustainable research data through a knowledge-driven ecosystem.

Does your service need to integrate / be interoperable with this service?

- Yes.
- No, integration does not make sense.
- No, integration is plausible, but out of scope for becoming an NFDI4Energy Service.

Explain:

If the integration is required, how is the progress here?

- Integration is complete.
- Integration is in progress.
- Integration is planned.
- Not started yet.

OpenResearchKnowledgeGraph

The Open Research Knowledge Graph (ORKG) aims to describe research papers in a structured manner. With the ORKG, papers are easier to find and compare.

Does your service need to integrate / be interoperable with this service?

- Yes.
- No, integration does not make sense.
- No, integration is plausible, but out of scope for becoming an NFDI4Energy Service.

Explain:

If the integration is required, how is the progress here?

- Integration is complete.
- Integration is in progress.
- Integration is planned.
- Not started yet.

Compliance with NFDI4Energy Standards and Requirements

Metadata

NFDI4Energy publishes its recommendations for a standardized Metadata in Deliverable 4.3.2¹ – As soon as it is available, services need to comply with these Metadata recommendations.

¹ NFDI4Energy Metadata document: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17549282>

Technical and Organisational requirements

The software of a Service is open source:

Yes

No

Explain:

There is a clear **legal status** regarding usage of the service, the produced results, and the underlying codebase:

License of the codebase:

Yes

No

Explain:

Terms of Usage:

Yes

No

Explain:

Privacy Policy:

Yes

No

Explain:

The Service is in Operation, meaning **TRL 7-9**

Yes

No

Explain:

There Service has **Documentation** Pages:

Yes

No

Explain:

There are **Contact details for support** available:

Yes

No

Explain:

There is Appropriate Application Security (also note if sensitive data is stored by the service):

Yes

No

Explain:

Compliance with NFDI Standards – *Only needed if Service wants to become an NFDI Service*

The service has clearly defined **maintenance and update cycles**, technical **monitoring** (availability, response times, etc.), regular **security audits**, and is **operated in certified/sovereign environments**.

Yes

No

Explain:

There are verifiable Service Level Agreements (SLA) between operators and users (possibly also departments of the NFDI association), as well as transparent **regulations on data protection, IT security, legal certainty, and terms of use**.

Yes

No

Explain:

The service has an openly accessible **operating model** with transparent information on financial sustainability, legal ownership, and the responsibilities of the service operators.

Yes

No

Explain:

Appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure the **confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the service** and the processed data are implemented (e.g. ISO or BSI Basic Protection).

Yes

No

Explain: